

The “Health” of Public Health Experiences of Governance during the Covid-19 Crisis in Switzerland

Nolwenn BÜHLER

Anthropologist of biomedicine and health
Unisanté, University Center for General Medicine and Public Health, Lausanne
nolwenn.buhler@unisante.ch

Giulia BELLONI

Assistant Physician, Unisanté, University Center for General Medicine and Public Health, Lausanne

Didier WERNLI

Associate Professor, Global Studies Institute & Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Science, University of Geneva

Stéphanie MONOD

Professor, Head of the Department of Epidemiology and Health Systems
Unisanté, University Center for General Medicine and Public Health, Lausanne

Résumé – La « santé » de la santé publique : Expériences de gouvernance pendant la crise de la pandémie de Covid-19 en Suisse

Cet article examine la pandémie comme une crise qui a révélé la gouvernance de la santé. Il vise à rendre compte de la complexité des relations entre savoir, pouvoir et pratiques, en explorant la manière dont les personnes qui jouent un rôle stratégique dans les systèmes de santé et de sécurité en Suisse ont vécu la pandémie et organisé la réponse à celle-ci. En s'appuyant sur une série d'entretiens réalisés avec des représentant.e.s de la santé publique et de la sécurité, il documente trois versions différentes de la pandémie, en tant que menace 1. pour la santé de la population ; 2. pour le système de santé ; et 3. pour la société. Il montre comment ces visions ont façonné les types de réponse apportés à Covid et comment la légitimité d'intervenir a été négociée en termes d'expertise. Servant de révélateur et amplificateur, la crise pandémique agit ainsi comme un prisme au travers duquel la « santé » de la santé publique en Suisse est discutée.

Abstract

This paper examines the pandemic as a crisis that exposed the governance of health. It aims to account for the complexity of the relations between knowledge, power, and practices, by exploring how people who play a strategic role in the health and security systems in Switzerland experienced the pandemic and organized the response to it. Drawing on a series of interviews with public health and security representatives, we document three different enactments of the pandemic, as a threat 1. to the health of the population; 2. to the healthcare system; and 3. to society. We show how these enactments shaped the response given to Covid, and how legitimacy to intervene was negotiated in terms of expertise. Serving as a revealing and amplifying factor, the pandemic crisis thus acts as a prism through which the “health” of public health in Switzerland is discussed.

Mots-clés

Santé – Gouvernance – Crise – Pandémie de Covid-19

Keywords

Health – Governance – Crisis – Covid-19 pandemic

INTRODUCTION

In Switzerland, like in many other countries, the Covid-19 pandemic exposed the domain of public health: its science, its policies, and its authority were in the spotlight. For months, the curves of deaths, hospitalizations, and infected cases punctuated daily life, and people got acquainted with cryptic notions such as the famous “ R_e ” for effective reproduction rate, or the difference between a PCR test and an antigenic one. The scientific evidence was mobilized to orient decisions, while the role of state authorities in charge of protecting the population, but also the functioning of the healthcare system, became objects of debates, not only in expert circles, but also in the population at large.

Faced with an emerging infectious disease and in a context of great uncertainties, authorities across the world took unprecedented measures and suspended individual liberties in the name of health. This regime of exception was enacted in many different ways according to national biopolitical traditions. The governing of life, in the Foucauldian sense (Foucault 2004), or biopolitical “interventions oriented to the preservation of life” were everywhere (Fassin & Fourcade 2022, p. 2). Yet, each emergency regime was specific and weighed differently in terms of the moral “goods” of health, security, and economy. For example, in Florida (US), a regime of “governance with contagion” during the pandemic prioritized economic interest, thereby harming health, and advancing other social divisions and exclusions (Kline 2023). In Israel, governmental intervention took the form of “encapsulation” to manage the pandemic (Rabi, Samimian-Darash & Hilberg 2022), understood in regard to actual uncertainty and the importance of the “milieu” as “the space of ‘possible events in which the State operates in regulating the population’” (Shoshana & Samimian-Darash 2014, p. 1152). Whereas in Switzerland, a federal country of 9 million inhabitants, a flexible regime of governing the crisis unfolded, relying mostly on individual responsibility and the moralization of protective behaviors (Bühler & al. 2022).

While the state power over individual lives was striking during the first wave, cracks and fragilities also appeared everywhere. Uncertainties, misinformation, and contradictions abounded. The unpreparedness of health systems, the difficult working conditions in hospitals, the shortage of masks, tests, and artificial respirators shed light on the neoliberal management of health institutions working “in just-in-time flux”, and austerity politics implemented long before the pandemic began (Gaudillière, Izambert & Juven 2021). The pandemic also brought to the surface the stark inequalities affecting lives and the failure of government and health authorities to protect those who had difficult working conditions, suffered from chronic conditions, were socially deprived, unable to access healthcare, or living in poor, densely-populated areas (Manderson, Burke & Wahlberg 2021).

In this paper, we examine the pandemic as a crisis that “exposed” the “normal unfolding of everyday life”, enabling us to explore the “new imaginaries, latent forces, ruptures and realignments”, as well as the “veiled social divisions that never go away” (Fassin & Fourcade 2022, p. 6), to reflect on the becoming of public health through the experiences of governmental officers involved in managing the Covid-19 crisis. As the crisis unfolded, the concept of resilience gained in visibility, in both public discourses and the scientific literature (Turenne & al. 2019). Resilience can be defined as “the capacities of natural and human systems to prevent, react to and recover from shocks” (Wernli & al. 2021). Originally designating the physical capacity of a metal to regain its initial shape after a shock, this notion has since been used in psychology to valorize humans’ ability to recover from traumatic events (Ollier-Malaterre 2010). When discourses of resilience are used to govern disasters, such as the Fukushima nuclear catastrophe, they tend to convey a positive idea of infinite adaptability, which translates into an individualized injunction to adapt to crises, rather than questioning the underlying economic and political forces generating disasters in the first place (Ribault 2021). By defining the Covid-19 pandemic as an acute, external threat, outside of human agency, and by valorizing adaptative resources, narratives of resilience may have contributed to invisibilizing existing more pressing political issues, such as the chronic crises affecting the healthcare system and the way the pandemic worsened those (Chabrol & David 2023).

The anthropology of policy (Shore & Wright 2003) investigates how policies work as instruments of governance, how they construct their political legitimacy, and shape subjectivity and identity. More specifically, health systems have been at the core of medical anthropology since the beginning of the field, yet not in a cohesive way (Closser & al. 2022). This literature recalls that health systems are social systems, in the sense of being organized socially and made up through social and power relations between individuals. Health systems are historically shaped, locally situated, and determined by a series of local and global factors which may have little to do with health *per se* (Baer,

Singer & Susser 2013, Closser & al. 2022). Taking policy makers and health professionals as our entry point and documenting how policies are produced, used, and with which effects, this sub-field provides insights into the economics, politics, and governance of health systems, as well as the cultural and normative assumptions underlying health policies, agendas, and institutions.

Abundant literature documents the various governance regimes adopted throughout the world during the pandemic, sometimes comparing them (i.e. Boin & al. 2020, Collins, Florin & Renn 2020, Dodds & al. 2020, Haug & al. 2020, Karaseva 2020, Lindsay, Baker & Calder-Dawe 2022). Many articles have, for example, explored the role of trust in the pandemic governance (i.e. Greer & al. 2022, Min & al. 2020, Oude Groeniger & al. 2021), or its biopolitical implications (Keck & Macia 2023, Kline 2023, Rabi & al. 2022). Yet, thick empirical research on the actual practices, constraints, and margin of maneuver of policy makers and state representatives are still scarce (Graaff, Bal & Bal 2021). In public discourses as well, the complexity of healthcare governance tends to be reduced and homogenized under “the state” category (Bergeron & al. 2020). It is therefore important to examine closely the dynamics of change at stake in the pandemic governance, not only to understand how a system or an organization can be “resilient”, but to grasp in more depth the underlying norms, values, knowledge, and power relations underlying practices, and the ways these match actual governance orientations.

Drawing on the critical medical anthropology of health and biomedicine (Fassin 2000, Lock & Nguyen 2018), the anthropology of epidemics (Kelly, Keck & Lynteris 2019) and the anthropology of health systems (Closser & al. 2022), we adopt a people-centered view to shed light on the health system “from within”. Through a qualitative analysis of the practices and experiences of actors on the governance frontline during the pandemic in Switzerland, we seek to understand “choices exercised by individuals or groups within the system, and the ways in which they do, or do not, exert control over processes by which that system-level resilience is shaped” (Topp 2020, p. 2). Our aim is therefore to account for the complexity of the relations between knowledge, power, and practices, by capturing how people who play a strategic role in the health and security systems in Switzerland experienced the pandemic and organized the response to it. We will describe the constraints as well as the agencies in which they were caught, thereby allowing us to expose the power dynamics at play in the governance of the pandemic.

More specifically, our study aims to account for the organizational reconfigurations and challenges encountered on the ground during the pandemic. We focus especially on two key aspects of resilience definition: the shock and the shape of the reaction, in Wernli et al.’s (2021) words, given to it. We turn to the concept of response-ability (Haraway 2016, p. 28), in order to apprehend the politics and ethics of resilience, by focusing on the ability to respond, that is, on the enabling conditions of possibility to respond, and the response as it was enacted in practice. This concept enables us to analyze the narrative, relational and situated dimension of response-ability to open up the normativity of a “good” resilient reaction, by paying attention to the possibilities of other kinds of relations between the actors involved, namely, public health and emergency authorities.

Thus, we document three different enactments of the “shock” of the pandemic, as a threat – 1. to the health of the population; 2. to the healthcare system; and 3. to society – which were all at risk in the management of the pandemic. We will show how these enactments shaped the kinds of reaction or response given to Covid, and how legitimacy to intervene was negotiated in terms of expertise. Serving as a revealing and amplifying factor, the pandemic crisis thus acts as a prism through which to discuss the “health” of public health in Switzerland. We take health in a double sense, as the health of public health as an institution, and health as this institution’s object of intervention. In this way we show how the blurred contours of what health means have significant implications for the working of public health and its governance, as an institution. Our research found the weakness of the public health domain and the multiple and contested definitions of its object, scope, and level of interventions that lie in it.

METHOD

This paper is based on a qualitative study of the resilience and governance of healthcare systems during the pandemic in three French-speaking cantons. It is part of a broader project consisting of a literature review and a legal report. For this qualitative subproject we conducted nine individual or collective interviews with health and security authorities in three cantons of the French-speaking part of Switzerland. Cantons are the main political subdivision in

Swiss health governance, as the Federal Council provides the general orientation of the healthcare system, but each of the 26 cantons has authority over its own health governance. We chose three cantons which vary in size, political orientation and health governance history, to gain contrasted insight into the challenges of the pandemic governance.

The individuals interviewed were chosen because of the key functions they played in the pandemic as governmental officers. We interviewed three categories of actors at the cantonal level of health governance. The first is cantonal doctors (CDs). They represent the medical authority and are legally in charge of protecting the population from infectious diseases, but the scope of their activity varies according to the cantons. The second category of actors is health department directors (HDs). They are in charge of allocating resources, delivering healthcare services, and developing health policies. The specific distribution of roles and responsibilities varies according to the socio-historical developments of each canton. The third category is chiefs of security departments (SDs). Pertaining historically to the military and civil security forces, they are mobilized during “extraordinary situations”, which, according to the Swiss Epidemic Act, means particular circumstances which threaten the population’s health, such as a highly infectious risk, but also other dangers affecting the economy or sectors considered to be “vital”, such as a disruption of energy provision or so-called “natural” disasters such as flooding. In contrast to the health authorities, this group is usually engaged in other professional responsibilities, and is only called in to play a leading crisis or emergency role in such extraordinary situations.

Due to the high visibility of their public functions, we have made maximal efforts to protect our interviewees’ anonymity, at their request. The table below summarizes abstract information about them. The age ranges are not shown as they were all between 45 and 60 years old. They all have a superior education level. The cantonal doctors and most health directors had trained as medical doctors, while the security directors and officers had followed police and military careers instead.

	Canton 1	Canton 2	Canton 3
Security directors (SDs)	Director and adjunct interviewed together (1W + 1M)	SD (1M) interviewed once	SD interviewed once
Cantonal doctors (CDs)	CD (1M) and HD (1M) interviewed together	CD and adjunct (2M) interviewed separately	Adjunct CD interviewed separately (1M)
Health directors (HDs)		HD interviewed twice (1 W)	& CD, HD & Head of Pharmacists interviewed together (1M + 2W)

M= Men, W= Women

The interviews were all conducted during 2022. They were audio-recorded, transcribed and analyzed with the assistance of Maxqda software. The results were discussed several times internally in the team. In 2023, we shared our initial findings from this qualitative subproject with the Cantonal Doctors’ Consortium. In 2024, we presented the results of all our subprojects to the actors involved in the project and other stakeholders working in health organizations, in security departments, or with vulnerable groups of the population at a workshop.

THE UNEXPECTED SHOCK OF THE FIRST WAVE

In Switzerland, a federal and liberal small country of almost 9 million inhabitants, the state organism in charge of public health is the Federal Office of Public Health (FOPH). Its mission is to protect the population, develop disease prevention programs, guidelines and regulations, as well as coordinate relations between insurance and healthcare providers in order to achieve this goal (Monod 2022). While the FOPH provides the main policy directions, cantons are responsible for protecting their population at the local level and have room for maneuver in allocating resources

and implementing their own health policies. This decentralized regulatory framework also makes space for private actors in the healthcare system, leaving room for the influences of various interest groups and political games (De Pietro & al. 2015).

On March 16, 2020, the Federal Council declared an “extraordinary situation” as defined in the Communicable Diseases Legislation (the Epidemic Act). This enabled it to impose the same national measures across all cantons. This period ended in June 2020, followed by a series of various measures and requirements given at the federal level and enforced variously by cantons. Measures changed rapidly according to the new tools available – vaccines, testing, etc – and the severity of the subsequent epidemic waves and new variants of the virus.

Two narratives about the resilience of the governance during the pandemic are weaved together: 1. the “romance” of the first wave, in the sense that it was idealized and overall experienced positively, from March to June 2020, which emerges as a very specific moment of cooperation, solidarity, creativity, and flexibility; and 2. the disillusioned story of exhaustion, frictions, and tensions that developed over time from the chronicization of the crisis. Both reveal different realities of the pandemic. This analysis first accounts for these contrasting narratives and then discusses the various enactments of the pandemic – the shock – to shed light on how they shaped the responsibility to the crisis.

1. The romance of the first wave: creativity, solidarity, and flexibility

“When we talked about Covid [we’d seen] on TV, no one, but no one, thought it was going to happen here, it was in China, it’s far away, China. No, nobody felt concerned by this thing, so there was no anticipation. There was a document that had been drawn up, a code of conduct, an assessment that had been done, but it had nothing to do with this crisis” (Security Director, Canton 1).

As this quote illustrates, the beginning of the pandemic was marked by the impression of living in an unexpected crisis, a shock whose scope and violence had not been anticipated. The extraordinary situation declared on March 16, 2020, and the semi-lockdown that was enforced, generated a sense of radical novelty. While most people were urged to stay at home, the health and security authorities were on the frontline, responsible for organizing the response to the pandemic in their respective cantons to protect the population. In the aftermath of the 2009 swine flu outbreak (H1N1) pandemic plans had been written, but all our health interviewees agreed that they were useless when the pandemic was declared, as one respondent explained:

“We know how it is in Switzerland, it is well organized, there are disaster plans for all situations, there are 100-page documents but when the crisis came nobody opened them (laughs) no, and then we managed on an ad hoc basis with lots of unknowns” (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 3).

While Switzerland is known for its safety culture, the preparedness plans that had been produced appeared pointless to the public health actors in charge of organizing the response when the pandemic occurred. The plans felt disconnected from the actual practical problems they were having to deal with, and were considered too long to read at a moment of great urgency¹. While at the global level, it seemed that fear went viral and countries adjusted their protection measures in comparison to the choices of other countries, at the local political level, actors in the health system explained how they had to “reinvent everything” and be “creative, flexible, agile” (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 3). Very quickly, they realized that the usual organization and assigned functions of their colleagues and employees would need to be reconfigured and activities reprioritized if they were to cope with the new demands and workload generated by organizing the pandemic response. The distribution of work and responsibilities had to be rethought, the functions and roles of professionals in their teams also needed to be reconsidered, as a health director explained:

“We immediately realized that we were up against the wall, I said to myself ‘we can’t go on like this’, so I went to the conference room, drew up an organization chart, called everyone in and said, ‘well, as of Monday morning, that’s how we’re going to work’. And then, out of the roughly 40 people working in the health department, I took half of them away from their usual duties...” (Health Director, Canton 1).

1. The only actor who reported that preparedness measures had been useful found that some practical role play training he had received had been useful, not the written plans.

While in ordinary times, this kind of authoritative act and immediate change could generate tensions – and probably did during the pandemic to some extent – the narratives of most actors we interviewed accounted for an initial highly stressful but overall positive, and even empowering, experience. People working in public health had to do new tasks, endorse new responsibilities, but they told us they felt united in a common goal to manage the crisis. The emergency feeling, the impression of living through something unique, a “historical moment”, demonstrated for example by the empty streets through which they drove to work, combined with the importance of feeling useful and of contributing concretely to a major crisis of global dimensions, of being on the frontline, was experienced as galvanizing for many.

Decision-making processes and the allocation of responsibilities and resources were “fluid”, “smooth”, “natural”. Due to uncertainties and a short decision-making cycle, decisions were often made rapidly, without taking the time to weigh up the costs and benefits, without official protocols to account for their rationale afterwards. Human or financial resources were procured via a phone call with a colleague. Usual power relations and competitive logics over the distribution of resources, or professional roles and responsibilities, were suspended by the gravity of the crisis, against which there was a need to join forces and stay united, the shock and the urgency working as common enemy against which to ally. For example, while often tensions and competition over resources or prestige taint relations among actors in the healthcare system, such as between private and public hospitals, relations of cooperation and solidarity predominated here. It reminded some of our respondents of the good atmosphere of the medical guards² when doctors are exhausted, have to deal with death, sickness, and suffering, but colleagues stick together to cope. They also expressed the pleasure of experiencing a powerful upswing feeling, as they were really on the frontline.

This first wave was characterized by the suspension of daily routines and institutional ways of doing. This whirlwind turned professional habits upside down and was remembered by public health actors as destabilizing but also experienced positively, with a sense of incredulity when faced with activities, tasks, and decisions that were thought impossible, but suddenly happened, with the pleasure of newness, creativity, and solidarity. A pragmatic logic turned towards the practical needs and immediate demands of the field predominated. Workable solutions had to be developed, which often required turning to other means than the usual state administration logics, to tinkering, and thinking less in terms of procedures and more in concrete and practical terms. Elements identified as favoring this pragmatic flexibility were the previous inter-knowledge between actors positioned at different key strategic points in the healthcare system. Knowing each other or having worked together in the past on other projects helped in the sense that collaboration was built on trust built up before the pandemic. This fostered mutual aid and solidarity between individuals, as the Cantonal Doctor and Health Director of Canton 3 explained:

“In hospital planning, we've integrated the clinics and we're used to working with them, so it's not, um, fierce competition like that, and that's how it is in the canton [speaking about a clinic which is on the border of the canton and not directly in its jurisdiction], well it wasn't, it wasn't really a problem, because there too we, we know each other, we manage to collaborate, ... we know each other well uh ... that's really the advantage of a small canton, we often say the roads are short, and it's really like that. I have the hospital director's phone number, and when there's a problem, we're able to call, and solutions have been found ... very quickly, very quickly ... Not for everything, but ...” [laughs].

Another element reported as supporting flexibility on the ground was assigning responsibilities and tasks to a person depending on their own strengths, skills and personality, rather than because of their determined function in an organigram. This was particularly evident in the narrative of the Cantonal Doctor of Canton 2:

“It was never formalized, it was decided, based on expertise, on desire... on, on opportunities, uh ... the fact that we hired X, that was also an opportunity, it wasn't planned anywhere, Y said to me one day, listen, for the schools it's going to be complicated, I need someone who's there during the vacations, who'll deputize for me at times when I only have to deal with epidemics etc., and then we said ah well, we'll hire X, who agreed and became Y's counterpart, ... and there's no pandemic plan in this library that says we had to hire X, you see, but you have to have that flexibility, i.e. when the expert comes in, and that worked very well with the politicians, every time I told them I needed

2. The term “medical guards” refers here to the work of physicians in clinical practices when they have to stay on-call in the hospital ward.

this, I needed that, that worked very well. So I repeat, you need charismatic leaders who can rely on mobile teams, who ... when you were talking about agility, that's it, but without it being plannable, you see..."

While a “romance” vision of the beginning of the pandemic predominated in the narratives of public health actors, the work it demanded and the fact that cooperation was never taken for granted also transpired. There were especially tensions with security actors from the beginning, with whom they were not used to collaborating on a daily basis, and frictions very quickly appeared, about who should govern the response and on the basis of which expertise. In fact, the reality of the crisis that emerged in security representatives’ narratives was slightly different from the start. In contrast with public health and medical actors, the role they took during the pandemic was distinct from that in their everyday professional lives. They only gained authority during the crisis due to the extraordinary situation declared by the Federal Council. While they agreed that the H1N1 plans were useless, they shared another idea about how disasters, emergencies, and crises need to be managed, based on a theoretical background about how to manage crises and their training in a military context. They depicted a clear, structured vision of the roles, missions and distribution of responsibility of each actor, inscribed in a predetermined hierarchical order. While the pandemic upset usual ways of doing for the health actors and led to important, yet momentary reorganizations, which were mostly experienced in a positive way, for the security actors, the pandemic provided an opportunity to apply and put into action the plans and theories of crisis management they had been prepared for. It was an opportunity for a real-life exercise where they could put their expertise to good effect.

2. In the long term: a shock of cultures

Under the inspired “romance” narrative of resilience, there was another narrative, marked by cracks, tensions, frictions, and exhaustion. In the fall of 2020, the state of “extraordinary situation” was changed to a “particular situation” according to the Law on Epidemics, which meant that the situation was deemed to be less serious, so measures controlling the population could be less stringent. This also gave cantons more room to maneuver in governing the crisis. This complicated the distribution of authority over decision making and the sharing of financial duties, between federal and cantonal levels, and generated diversity among cantons regarding the measures they adopted. In addition, the distribution of responsibility and leadership between security and health representatives shifted. While security officers had leadership during the first wave, the health authorities took over when the extraordinary situation was suspended. Tensions among the actors in charge of governing the pandemic were experienced and described as a shock between health and security “cultures”. These tensions are described as palpable and mostly took place during joint meetings. In fact, the crisis made visible a new category of actors, those stemming from security, which modified the usual power relations in crisis management.

Our argument is that this shock of “cultures” did not only relate to the pandemic itself and cannot be reduced to conflict between individuals with strong personalities and opinions, but emerged because there were different enactments of the pandemic which did not automatically align. Those entailed more than the pandemic itself. They involved whole cultures or social worlds, that is, different modes of organization, forms of expertise, and sets of professional practices. Fassin and Dozon (2001) propose to apprehend public health as a culture in itself, not only as it is influenced by national histories and politics, but also as being itself a social world made of human actors, politics, expertise, which tend to ignore and erase their social nature. Borrowing Hoeyer et al.’s words we can also speak of public health culture as a complex assemblage or “arrangements of practices, technologies, and theories that configure action in a sociotechnical space”(Hoeyer, Bauer & Pickersgill 2019, p. 460). The enactments involved different priorities and risk analyses, which could conflict. They also involved different forms of response-ability to the crisis. It might be assumed that there were only divergences between health and security actors. However, our analysis reveals more complexity. In fact, there were also divergences between cantonal doctors and health department officers. As the precise tasks and responsibilities they endorsed in each canton varied as well, this complicated the picture even more. Hence, the three main enactments of the pandemic related to the three functions of security, health departments, and cantonal doctors, each of which had different relations to the healthcare system and influenced crisis management in differing ways. In fact, they determined relations with politicians, the “Conseiller.ère.s d’État” (the cantons’ executives) who direct the security and health departments and hold power over human and financial resources and decision-making. Thus, power games were played to influence their decisions in the ways

the three categories of actors we interviewed seeked. Underlying these three main enactments, three visions of what (public) health is, or should and could be, also appeared in our interlocutors' accounts. These definitions were deeply entangled with their visions of what public health, as an institution, should do. The pandemic can thus be taken as a crucial episode through which to grasp different concepts of public health which might matter in the future.

2.1. The pandemic as an infectious threat to the population

Marked by an epidemiologic transition from infectious to chronic diseases, countries of the global north are nevertheless inscribed in a regime of preparedness and biosecurity that has focused on emerging viral threats since the beginning of the 2000s and outbreaks of zoonoses like mad cow disease, avian flu or H1N1, and Ebola (Bourrier, Burton-Jeangros & Bastide 2014, Caduff 2015). At the beginning of 2020, when images of comatose bodies on ventilators, overwhelmed intensive care units and exhausted healthcare professionals, coffins and distraught families started to circulate from Italy, it awakened the pandemic imaginary of human extinction (Lynteris 2020) associated with the preparedness regime. Military metaphors of the new coronavirus as an enemy against which a war had to be conducted were voiced by authorities (Brives 2020). This had implications for health governance. At the beginning of the pandemic, dissent or challenge was barely tolerated. People were quickly accused of being conspiracists if they dared criticize any aspect of pandemic management. While the war metaphor involved a top-down controlling form of crisis management, in Switzerland, a flexible regime was adopted instead. This framed the response to the pandemic as a fight against a virus which must be conducted collectively, but whose effectiveness rested primarily on individual responsibility. This illustrated the great neoliberal value granted to individual freedom and responsibility which predominates in Switzerland.

This framing of the pandemic as an emergency war-like regime contrasted with the narratives of some infectious disease specialists working as cantonal doctors who played a key role in the response. Legal responsibility for infectious diseases is part of their everyday business, and they regularly have to deal with seasonal influenza or outbreaks of measles. As a cantonal doctor expressed: *"My job is to control communicable diseases"* (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 2). The expertise of these actors draws on two sets of knowledge. The first is scientific – epidemiological, infectiology, transmissible diseases – and the second is experiential, stemming from about 10-15 years' practice in the field of infectious diseases:

"You see... you cannot invent communicable disease crisis management with people who've never dealt with even the smallest epidemic. And they're not, they're not people who, uh ... who have any knowledge of epidemiological analysis, risk analysis, uh ... so you have to be able to understand the issues, the risks, etc... so that's why I'm talking about, about an existing team, which works on a day-to-day basis, but at the same time plans things ahead, at a minimum" (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 2).

This kind of expertise shaped the kinds of responses given to the pandemic and their political and moral implications. Defining the shock as an "infectious threat" shaped these actors' main objective: to decrease the number of cases and contain the epidemic. Their analysis of risks was based on epidemiological statistics, monitoring in differentiated ways the number of cases, hospitalizations and deaths in different population groups, to anticipate outcomes and help decision making. Their vision was to develop measures based on this fined-grained epidemiological analysis, not to aim for "zero risk" for everyone, but to target and differentiate measures according to the local and social context. Their previous experiences had also taught them that sometimes to *"wait and do nothing"* (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 2) is the best way of managing a crisis. This therefore conveyed a temporality that was distinct from the urgency and dramatic tone of the pandemic portrayed as a rapid emergency. It also tended to restrict the understanding of health to the question of infections, prioritizing the objective of flattening infection and fatality curves and using epidemiological expertise in decision making.

Here health was apprehended mainly in terms of risk, contagion, and disease in the population. The social context or implications of the crisis were only taken into consideration with respect to the ways they shaped contaminations. The closure of restaurants and cultural places raised many debates, for example, where the absence of epidemiological evidence of contamination was advanced by these cantonal medical authorities to counter the decisions taken. The closure of schools was also debated in regard to children's role in spreading the coronavirus. Based on their expertise in infectious diseases, cantonal doctors in some cantons disagreed with their closure, not for psychological or social reasons, but as the most efficient way of containing the epidemic. While federal measures promulgated over

the course of the pandemic had a one-size-fits-all dimension, the cantons had room for maneuver to differentiate them more, room in which epidemiological expertise on infectious diseases was repeatedly put forward to defend some measures over others, ahead of other security and healthcare systems actors, and especially the politicians who were ultimately taking the decisions on these measures.

2.2. The pandemic as a threat to the healthcare system

Some of the government officers in charge of the health system, of the planification and development of policies, did not immediately feel concerned by the pandemic being framed as an infectious disease. However, it quickly became clear that the health system would be affected and that it was the main target of measures aiming to contain the epidemic, as a health director explained:

“So right away, in fact, it's the image of a very deadly virus arriving, a virus that's going to mow people down and suffocate them, so to cut a long story short, I said, we absolutely must avoid too many people going to hospital, because the hospital will be completely overwhelmed. So we have to reduce the number of people going into hospital as much as possible, and to do that, we absolutely have to tell the whole system to maintain and increase its capacity to provide care in the community, so we have to strengthen all the systems that provide care beyond what they usually do, even for people they would otherwise send to hospital, so the first thing was to reduce the funnel to hospital and emergency services, and the second thing was to say, we could see that elderly people were dying, and we said here in elderly homes we absolutely have to set up the system so that people die as comfortably as possible in an EMS (elderly nursing home). We mustn't take them out” (Health Director, Canton 2).

For these actors, who mostly had health direction functions³, the pandemic was framed as a threat to the health system, so the health system became the target of interventions in order to be able to keep providing care, while cantonal doctors focused more directly on the collective body of the population, understood in the epidemiological sense of the given population in which a virus circulates. Having an overview of the whole system – healthcare professionals, clinics and hospitals' representatives and functions, but also community and social health teams – and knowing them through different previous projects, these actors did not focus on counting infection rates or differentiating measures according to the ways the virus circulates among people. The indicators they needed were those of the health system – how many beds were free in healthcare facilities, how crowded were the intensive care units, how bad was the shortage of healthcare professionals – and the pandemic revealed the lack of a preexisting data infrastructure that would enable them to monitor the health of the health system, as they told us they would have needed.

Their focus was also different in the sense that managing the pandemic had to be done on top of all their other tasks: *“we had a system to run”* (Health Director, Canton 3). Furthermore, their expertise and ways of working were different, as they were used to slow administration times, trained in the state administration career path, not necessarily in medicine, even less in emergency medicine. Deemed as being too reflexive and intellectual by others, the culture of work they were used to was structured by administrative and state logics. Yet in pandemic times, when they had to reorganize and reprioritize all their activities, the culture they favored was more horizontal and cooperative. For example, in some cantons the crisis gave rise to interesting organizational innovations such a weekly online meeting of all those actors in the health system willing to participate:

“Typically things that have worked well are, um ... it was the, the local genius, when my colleagues [Health Direction colleagues] decided to bring together all our partners in the health system once a day, and then once a week at a given time, it was useful to do it, it worked well, but we'd never imagined it like that” (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 2).

This new meeting was open to all health professionals, the invitation was circulated and no control was exercised over exactly who could participate. It involved only minimal technology, access to the internet and creating a Zoom link, repeated every week. It enabled strategic information, such as the degree of exhaustion or absenteeism in a medical service, or the epidemic peaks that were observed in one place or another, to be shared in a way which circumvented usual institutional paths. The interdependence among actors, their mutual needs, the information

3. The distribution of tasks and roles between CDs and HDs was not clearly defined, according to the cantons. Therefore, while the two visions emerged distinctly, they did not precisely cover the function of the actors interviewed, who are quoted in this paper.

sharing between them, and the consciousness that they needed to work in solidarity to make the health system stand up to the shock, predominated in the experience they reported. For them, health meant the health of the health system more than the health of the population as a whole, but the social implications of measures taken for the population and the healthcare systems were also considered. For instance, the deferral of “non-urgent consultations” decreed by the Federal Council raised many concerns in regard to its impact on people’s health:

“When the Federal Council expressed that doctors should only do urgent consultations, we reacted very strongly, saying that we didn’t understand, if the goal in the long term, with family doctors, is to avoid crowding emergency services, then it’s precisely necessary to keep doing medical consultations, for prevention and to avoid emergencies. So we said we’re taking measures to fight against what, against infections, respiratory viruses, which for most people don’t do any damage, but we’re preventing comprehensive care in the population, which will do damage. We said that, and I assure you that even our heads of department, they were tired of hearing us in the end. I can understand them, because we kept saying, no, no, no...” (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 2).

This example illustrates how some measures were criticized by advocating a broader perspective on the healthcare system and defending the need to maintain core health services for all patients. It also shows how difficult it was for such voices to be heard in a political context where the expertise and vision of health representatives was subordinated to politicians’ decision making. In some places and moments, these differences of culture within public health – epidemic focused vs healthcare system focused – gave rise to tensions about the governance of the pandemic and the distribution of roles and authority, about who should decide, and whose vision should prevail over others. The complementarity of the combined expertise was also recognized, and alliances made over time to defend some decisions to politicians. As the final decisions were taken by the politicians, work to convince them was undertaken and different tactics were mobilized to get these voices heard. These involved, for example, being seated at a specific place in the parliamentary room where decisions were being taken, speaking at strategic moments, or insisting that every meeting must start by reviewing epidemiological and healthcare statistics. Governmental health officers also expressed a lot of disillusionment at these constant back-and-forths between their observations and expertise and their negotiations with politicians. In this regard, there were important differences between cantons, depending on the political orientation of their government – whether they were more on the left or the right – and the level of finances in each, as some cantons invest more in their health system than others.

2.3. The pandemic as a disaster threatening economy and society

“I think we also had a lot of trouble getting them [the health authorities] to understand something, which is that there aren’t separate worlds between the health world, the economic world, the cultural world, the associative world. At some point, when we’re faced with a health crisis, it’s systemic. It affects every field, and so we need to get all these fields working together... And to imagine that we can entrust the management of a health crisis to the health authorities is to make an extremely serious mistake from a strategic point of view. Because in today’s society it’s no longer possible... it’s too systemic, you have to develop an absolutely cross-disciplinary approach, with the resolution of the health problem at the center of your concerns, that’s clear, but which must take into account everything else and have this broader picture in mind about where is the balance in the sacrifices made, versus the benefits obtained?” (Security Director, Canton 1).

This vision of pandemic governance enlarged the two previous perspectives, as it insisted on the interlocking of several worlds and the need to join various types of expertise to address its complexity. Health sciences, medical expertise, and the healthcare system are only individual pieces of a broader – societal – puzzle. This perspective was at odds with the vision of health representatives who defended the need for on the ground expertise in managing infectious diseases and health, defending the idea that: *“it was a health problem, so we had to listen to health experts”* (Cantonal Doctor, Canton 2).

For public security authorities the object of the crisis was not the main point – it would not matter whether it was a pandemic, a pollution, or an earthquake. What mattered was a systemic and strategic vision which rested on pre-determined theories of crisis management: *“To manage a crisis situation, you have procedures, methods, decision making has to be quick, but it is structured and analytical to reach your objective. So our know-how, our expertise is there”* (Security Director, Canton 3).

These actors saw their expertise less in relation to the nature of the shock itself, but in the organization of the response – coordinating, providing resources where and when needed, and assisting experts, by providing a centralized and systematic view of the situation. For them, decision making must be strategic and analytic, and action aimed towards clear objectives, the distribution of roles and tasks independent from the individuals themselves. Their reference to, and sometimes experience of, war situations, was mobilized as a model for governing the crisis. They also viewed their role as providing the logistical and coordination support health experts might need, for example, to build a vaccination center in a few days or to put health departments in contact with others, to get more support. Efficiency and control over action predominated in this emergency culture, and health was only one aspect of the situation they took into consideration. They defended a broader systemic view of the impact of the shock, framed as a threat for society, and especially the economy.

Their military tone and culture, and the ways they entered the domain of health, generated shocks and frictions with the health managers, whether cantonal doctors or health directors. Frictions over the crisis management in terms of decision making, resource allocating, and priority setting, crystalized in terms of differing expertise. Expertise of infectious diseases and the healthcare system was advanced to legitimize the authority of health representatives over security representatives, who in contrast, put forward their expertise in terms of emergency management, logistics, and strategy. Over time, they all recognized that they had learned from and taken inspiration from each other. This gain in experiential knowledge was used later on for the Ukrainian and the energy crisis:

“So it was the health department that took over, because for the Council of State and for the authority in charge of health, it was important that it remained in health professional hands, but in fact we were in a crisis, and once again, the notion of a crisis is not understood by everyone. When you have a crisis, there are lots of impacts, it's not just one department, it's not just one entity, as we've seen with Ukraine, there are lots of impacts, there are lots of people, there are lots of things to think about, there are lots of entities and that ... well, that's something you learn and then, not everyone ... everyone is a specialist in their own field, everyone knows their own field, they're not going to deal with it... we're experiencing it now... I see it with energy, I have the same problem because the heads of department, my colleagues who are concerned, they don't feel, depending on their field, okay, but they don't feel... we're waiting for the Confederation to press the button and then, when the Confederation... we'll go into action, whereas crisis management requires anticipation, it requires an understanding of the problem, it requires coordination, it requires anticipation so that when it arrives, we've already thought of a certain number of things and then we manage all the unforeseen events, because there will be lots and lots of little things added on, in fact” (Security Director, Canton 3).

In this last enactment of the shock and response to a crisis, a broad societal and systemic vision combined with security principles of preparedness, strategy, and action. The broader vision of the pandemic governance thus went hand in hand with a military culture of security and a vertical kind of governance.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The governance of the Covid-19 pandemic in Switzerland was a matter of biopolitics. The role of the state in governing life through interventions which aimed to protect and preserve the life of the population became highly visible. Ultimately, political decisions, surveillance, and control were exerted over people's lives, in the name of health, in the name of saving lives, in the name of protecting the most vulnerable. Exploring how health and security government officers experienced the governance of the pandemic reveals a more complex version of these biopolitics. Rather than apprehending the state as a homogeneous entity, the focus on experiences and practices of governing the crisis allows us to see the diffractions and heterogeneity that make up the social world of public health. Like the HIV pandemic in the early '90s, the Covid pandemic serves both as an analyzer and a catalyzer (Hintermeyer 2003). On the one hand it exposed the multiplicity and divergences at play in the governing of the Covid-19 crisis. On the other hand, it accelerated, accentuated, and sometimes even worsened preexisting dynamics and power relations. Adopting a human-centered approach has made it clear that biopolitics is a matter of micropolitics, by revealing the blurry contours of what public health is. A realm in which behind the governance of the pandemic as a crisis, the everyday governance of health is at stake. In which, underneath the romance narrative of cooperation, solidarity, and pragmatic flexibility, cracks, frictions and tensions emerged over decision making, resource allocating, and priority setting.

Following Mol and Hardon's (2020) analysis that the pandemic was enacted in multiple ways, we argue that there were different enactments of the shock which entailed different forms of response-ability, that is, different ways of responding to the crisis and envisioning its governance. We identified three different cultures – assemblages of infrastructure, expertise, interventions, and organization in practice – which enacted differently both the “shock” and the “response” to it. In the first one, the shock, or the pandemic, was framed as an infectious disease threatening the population. What mattered here in terms of expertise was how the virus circulated from one body to the other, and how many bodies got contaminated. Health was defined in terms of the ability of bodies to suffer, transmit, or resist viral loads. Individual health was only considered significant when clustered in epidemiological statistics which made visible the power of the virus to affect the corpus of the population. These were used to orient decision making by anticipating the next move of the virus. The “social body” (for an analysis of the biological metaphor of society as the ‘social body’ see Hintermeyer 1993) was not absent from these considerations, which aimed to target interventions in a differentiated way according to the milieu and context of contaminations.

In the second culture, it was the health of the healthcare system which mattered, that is, how it could keep functioning in an efficient way. Here, the pandemic was enacted as a threat to the healthcare system's ability to fulfill its missions, which also became the target of interventions. This involved taking a distributed and systemic view of healthcare. The health of healthcare professionals, the number of beds available in intensive care units, the ways private and public clinics might cooperate, the possible engagement of general practitioners, the community health teams working with people considered to be vulnerable socially or medically, became strategic issues. Individual health mattered in its encounters with the healthcare systems, as patients entered and left hospitals and circulated from one service to the other, and people were born and died in its facilities. The healthcare system's health had to be protected, with barriers erected against the coronavirus by restricting access, deferring non-urgent consultations, and limiting visits, but also protected against the prospect of its own breakdown. It needed to hold the shock at any cost and keep its community-based projects vitalized and sustained.

Thirdly, the pandemic was enacted as a shock affecting the health of society as a whole. Health in its restricted definition is understood medically, but during the pandemic what mattered was the health of society, including its economic activities, which were needed to keep money flows circulating, and avoid spending all the resources on a disease which ultimately did not drastically change the demography of the population. What mattered was the ability to maintain social relations and cultural activities necessary to keep society alive. It was recognized that the deleterious impact of restraining social and cultural activities over a long time would impact mental health and might cost as much in the long term (i.e. Diaz Hernandez & al. 2021). Society was envisioned as a systemic whole with strategic points to identify and protect, or places to intervene to reduce viral circulation. This response unfolded through logistics and strategic know-how, coordinating operational activities, centralizing data and information. This culture of security positioned its professionals at the heart of a social organism whose systems – medical, economic, educational, etc. – had to be coordinated and synchronized. Medical expertise was acknowledged but not seen as sufficient to take leadership over decisions which would impact society as a whole.

We also found that these cultures had different governance styles, from an action-oriented one resting on the individual potential of professionals, to the military vertical, authoritarian style of the security culture, and the more horizontal, cooperative, and inclusive style which revitalized the health of the healthcare system, which is sometimes sclerosed by administrative logics. While frictions were expressed as a shock of cultures in the governance of the pandemic, we argue that these cultures engaged whole worlds with them and visions of what the shock was, how it affected health, and how one should respond to it. The pandemic was not only “multiple” at an epistemic level, as an infectious threat, i.e. a threat to individuals, a threat to the healthcare system, and a threat to society. The different enactments of the shock had also implication for governance. They were embedded in forms of expertise and organization modes, which indeed involved different ways of governing the crisis and agreeing who should lead it. The negotiations around the unclear perimeter of health, and about who was responsible for the population's health so should take the lead in decision making, resource allocating, and communicating, is telling about the structural weaknesses of public health as an institution, but also about the blurry contours of what health is and how it should be protected in the first place. What emerges from our study is not only that public health as a domain is not well defined, but that the crisis opens up other questions: what is a “healthy population”? Does it concern the health of the population in terms of physical, mental and social well-being, of the healthcare system and its vulnerable groups, or rather the whole of society, taken as a body, whose functions need to be protected? Taking into account the less visible but

chronic environmental crisis that is nevertheless the most urgent challenge societies and health actors are currently facing, we question the absence of reference to ecology and the climate in our interviewees' reflections on the governing of the crisis, at odds with the importance of thinking about health beyond the human (Whitmee & al. 2015). At a moment in which discourses around the crisis of the health system abound, it is worth continuing to explore the pandemic, not only as a way to learn lessons about how to make the system more resilient, but to keep reflecting on how it exposed the multiple definitions of what health, and a life worth living, are, and as an invitation to think about the kind of public health cultures we have, and would like to sustain, in the future.

This paper reflects on the pandemic experiences of health and security actors in three cantons of the French-speaking part of Switzerland. As the visions of health, politics, the importance granted to the state and individual responsibility greatly differ between the French- and German speaking areas of the country, it would be interesting to pursue this inquiry within German-speaking cantons. There was also a retrospective dimension to the study which inevitably taints the narratives collected and analyzed. As the different enactments of the shock of the pandemic emerged in different cultures of public health and security and involved different forms of response-ability, there is a practical need to create, maintain, and sustain spaces of encounter for these different social worlds to meet and enter into dialogue. This study has shown that, when people are used to working together, this facilitates their cooperation in times of crisis, as they already know and trust each other. Thus, in a spirit of preparedness, it seems more important than ever to improve translation processes, mutual understandings of ways of working, and alignment possibilities, whilst acknowledging inevitable dissent (Kraus 2012). Especially as budget restrictions in regard to the health domain are currently being imposed in Switzerland, justified by the need to recover from the financial expenses of Covid, there is a need to ally forces and collectively assert what kind of health we want to defend and what the role and scope of interventions in public health might, or should be, in the face of the pressing existing challenges of rising inequalities and climate crisis.

Références

- Baer, H. A., Singer, M., & Susser, I. (2013), *Medical Anthropology and the World System: Critical Perspectives, 3rd Edition: Critical Perspectives*, Santa Barbara, Denver, Oxford, Praeger.
- Bergeron, H., Borraz, O., Castel, P., & Dedieu, F. (2020), *Covid-19 : Une crise organisationnelle*, Paris, Presses de Sciences Po.
- Boin, A., Brock, K., Craft, J., Halligan, J., 't Hart, P., Roy, J., Tellier, G., & Turnbull, L. (2020), Beyond COVID-19: Five commentaries on expert knowledge, executive action, and accountability in governance and public administration, *Canadian Public Administration*, 63(3), p. 339–368. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/capa.12386>
- Bourrier, M., Burton-Jeangros, C., & Bastide, L. (2014), Sous surveillance : Possibilités et limites du régime de la preparedness. Le cas de la pandémie A (H1N1), *Socio-anthropologie*, 29, p. 157–171. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/socio-anthropologie.1723>
- Brives, C. (2020, June 1), Pluribiose. Vivre avec les virus. Mais comment ? *Terrestres*. <https://www.terrestres.org/2020/06/01/pluribiose-vivre-avec-les-virus-mais-comment/>
- Bühler, N., Pralong, M., Burnand, C., Rawlinson, C., Nusslé, S. G., D'Acremont, V., Bochud, M., & Bodenmann, P. (2022), "Flexible Lockdown" in Switzerland: Individual Responsibility and the Daily Navigation of Risk and Protection. In *Negotiating the Pandemic*, London, New York, Routledge, p. 110-124.
- Caduff, C. (2015), *The Pandemic Perhaps: Dramatic Events in a Public Culture of Danger*, Oakland, Univ of California Press.
- Chabrol, F., & David, P.-M. (2023), How resilience affected public health research during COVID-19 and why we should abandon it, *Global Public Health*, 18(1), p. 2212750. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17441692.2023.2212750>
- Closser, S., Mendenhall, E., Brown, P., Neill, R., & Justice, J. (2022), The anthropology of health systems: A history and review, *Social Science & Medicine*, 300, p. 114314. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114314>
- Collins, A., Florin, M.-V., & Renn, O. (2020), COVID-19 risk governance: Drivers, responses and lessons to be learned, *Journal of Risk Research*, 23(7–8), p. 1073–1082. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2020.1760332>
- De Pietro, C., Camenzind, P., Sturny, I., Crivelli, L., Edwards-Garavoglia, S., Spranger, A., Wittenbecher, F., & Quentin, W. (2015), Switzerland: Health System Review, *Health Systems in Transition*, 17(4), p. 1–288, xix.
- Diaz Hernandez, L., Giezendanner, S., Fischer, R., & Zeller, A. (2021), The effect of COVID-19 on mental well-being in Switzerland: A cross-sectional survey of the adult Swiss general population, *BMC Family Practice*, 22(1), p. 181. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-021-01532-7>
- Dodds, K., Broto, V. C., Detterbeck, K., Jones, M., Mamadouh, V., Ramutsindela, M., Varsanyi, M., Wachsmuth, D., & Woon, C. Y. (2020), The COVID-19 pandemic: Territorial, political and governance dimensions of the crisis, *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 8(3), p. 289–298. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2020.1771022>

- Dozon, J.-P., & Fassin, D. (2001), *Critique de la santé publique: Une approche anthropologique*. Paris, Balland.
- Fassin, D. (2000), Entre politiques du vivant et politiques de la vie: Pour une anthropologie de la santé, *Anthropologie et Sociétés*, 24(1), p. 95–116. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7202/015638ar>
- Fassin, D., & Fourcade, M. (Eds.). (2022), *Pandemic Exposures: Economy and Society in the Time of Coronavirus*, London, HAU.
- Foucault, M. (2004), *La Naissance de la biopolitique. Cours au Collège de France*, Paris, SEUIL.
- Gaudillière, J.-P., Izambert, C., & Juven, P.-A. (2021), *Pandémopolitique: Réinventer la santé en commun*, Paris, La Découverte.
- Graaff, B. de, Bal, J., & Bal, R. (2021), Layering risk work amidst an emerging crisis: An ethnographic study on the governance of the COVID-19 pandemic in a university hospital in the Netherlands, *Health, Risk & Society*, 0(0), p. 1–17. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698575.2021.1910210>
- Greer, S. L., Rozenblum, S., Falkenbach, M., Löblová, O., Jarman, H., Williams, N., & Wismar, M. (2022), Centralizing and decentralizing governance in the COVID-19 pandemic: The politics of credit and blame, *Health Policy*, 126(5), p. 408–417. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2022.03.004>
- Haraway, D. J. (2016), *Staying With the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Durham, North Carolina, Duke University Press.
- Haug, N., Geyrhofer, L., Londei, A., Dervic, E., Desvars-Larrive, A., Loreto, V., Piniór, B., Thurner, S., & Klimek, P. (2020), Ranking the effectiveness of worldwide COVID-19 government interventions, *Nature Human Behaviour*, p. 1–10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-020-01009-0>
- Hintermeyer, P. (1993), Imaginaires du corps social, *Revue des Sciences Sociales*, 20, p. 192-197. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3406/revss.1993.3596>
- Hintermeyer, P. (2003), Le rapport au sida, un observatoire social, *Revue des Sciences Sociales*, 31, p. 212-217. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3406/revss.2003.2667>
- Hoeyer, K., Bauer, S., & Pickersgill, M. (2019), Datafication and accountability in public health: Introduction to a special issue, *Social Studies of Science* 49 (4), pp. 459–475.
- Karaseva, A. (2020), The legal void and COVID-19 governance, *Social Anthropology*, 28(2), p. 294–295. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-8676.12825>
- Keck, F., & Macia, E. (2023), The government of masks in sentinel territories against Covid-19: Dakar and Seine-Saint-Denis, *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), p. 1291. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15968-2>
- Kelly, A. H., Keck, F., & Lynteris, C. (Eds.). (2019), *The Anthropology of Epidemics*. Milton Park, Taylor & Francis. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429461897>
- Kline, N. (2023), Governing with contagion: Pandemic politics, COVID-19, and undermining public health in Florida, *Medical Anthropology Quarterly*, 37 (4), p. 367-381. <https://doi.org/10.1111/maq.12806>
- Kraus, C. (2012), Linking Neuroscience, Medicine, Gender and Society through Controversy and Conflict Analysis: A “Dissensus Framework” for Feminist/Queer Brain Science Studies, In R. Bluhm, A. J. Jacobson, & H. L. Maibom (Eds.), *Neurofeminism: Issues at the Intersection of Feminist Theory and Cognitive Science* (pp. 193–215), London, New York, Shanghai, Palgrave Macmillan UK. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230368385_10
- Lindsay, N., Baker, T., & Calder-Dawe, O. (2022), Mental coaching through crisis: Digital technologies and psychological governance during COVID-19, *Critical Public Health*, 32(1), p. 104–115. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09581596.2021.1965543>
- Lock, M., & Nguyen, V.-K. (2018), *An Anthropology of Biomedicine*, Hoboken, New Jersey, John Wiley & Sons.
- Lynteris, C. (2020), *Human Extinction and the Pandemic Imaginary*. Milton Park, Taylor & Francis. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429322051>
- Manderson, L., Burke, N. J., & Wahlberg, A. (Eds.). (2021). *Viral Loads: Anthropologies of urgency in the time of COVID-19*. London, UCL Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781800080232>
- Min, C., Shen, F., Yu, W., & Chu, Y. (2020), The relationship between government trust and preventive behaviors during the COVID-19 pandemic in China: Exploring the roles of knowledge and negative emotion, *Preventive Medicine*, 141, p. 106288. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2020.106288>
- Mol, A., & Hardon, A. (2020), What COVID-19 may teach us about interdisciplinarity, *BMJ Global Health*, 5(12), p. e004375. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-004375>
- Monod, S. (2022), Système de santé suisse: Aux origines de la machine, *Revue Médicale Suisse*, 18(793), p. 1617–1620. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53738/REVMED.2022.18.793.1617>
- Ollier-Malaterre, A. (2010), From Conciliation to Resilience: 40 Years of Lexical Evolution in the United States, *Travail, genre et sociétés*, 24(2), p. 111–128.
- Oude Groeniger, J., Noordzij, K., van der Waal, J., & de Koster, W. (2021), Dutch COVID-19 lockdown measures increased trust in government and trust in science: A difference-in-differences analysis, *Social Science & Medicine*, 275, p. 113819. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.113819>

- Rabi, M., Samimian-Darash, L., & Hilberg, E. (2022), Encapsulation: Governing actual uncertainty in the coronavirus pandemic, *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 44(3), p.586–603. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.13436>
- Ribault, T. (2021), *Contre la résilience: A Fukushima et ailleurs* (1er édition), Paris, L'Echappée.
- Shore, C., & Wright, S. (2003), *Anthropology of Policy: Perspectives on Governance and Power*. Milton Park, Routledge.
- Shoshana, A., & Samimian-Darash, L. (2014), Governing Heterogeneous Populations: 'Separate and Unequal' in Israel, *Sociology*, 48(6), p. 1139–1155. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038513512730>
- Topp, S. M. (2020), Power and politics: The case for linking resilience to health system governance, *BMJ Global Health*, 5(6), p. e002891. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-002891>
- Turenne, C. P., Gautier, L., Degroote, S., Guillard, E., Chabrol, F., & Ridde, V. (2019), Conceptual analysis of health systems resilience: A scoping review, *Social Science & Medicine*, 232, p. 168–180. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2019.04.020>
- Wernli, D., Clausin, M., Antulov-Fantulin, N., Berezowski, J., Biller-Andorno, N., Blanchet, K., Böttcher, L., Burton-Jeangros, C., Escher, G., Flahault, A., Fukuda, K., Helbing, D., Jaffé, P. D., Jørgensen, P. S., Kaspiarovich, Y., Krishnakumar, J., Lawrence, R. J., Lee, K., Léger, A., ... Young, O. (2021), Building a multisystemic understanding of societal resilience to the COVID-19 pandemic, *BMJ Global Health*, 6(7), p. e006794. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-006794>
- Whitmee, S., Haines, A., Beyrer, C., Boltz, F., Capon, A. G., Dias, B. F. de S., Ezech, A., Frumkin, H., Gong, P., Head, P., Horton, R., Mace, G. M., Marten, R., Myers, S. S., Nishtar, S., Osofsky, S. A., Pattanayak, S. K., Pongsiri, M. J., Romanelli, C., ... Yach, D. (2015), Safeguarding human health in the Anthropocene epoch: Report of The Rockefeller Foundation–Lancet Commission on planetary health, *The Lancet*, 386(10007), p. 1973–2028. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(15\)60901-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(15)60901-1)